

The effect of BIM in AEC Education: an empirical study

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Abstract

The purpose of the thesis is to investigate if and how Building Information Modelling (BIM) has been affecting university level architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) education around the world. It is based on the theoretical scenarios from literature for BIM's impact. A survey was conducted among the community of professors and researchers involved with BIM/IT, which were contacted by email. 921 invitations were sent, and 125 replies received from 6 continents but most from North America, Europe, and Asia. In addition to a questionnaire comprising of 20 questions in Google Forms, interview with selected respondents were conducted via videoconference. We are finding that even though there are many challenges, BIM has indeed already transformed education, prompting a reevaluation of how interdisciplinary knowledge is integrated and enhancing students' preparedness for collaborative work in the AEC industry. Also, there's a deliberate effort to steer away from framing BIM as a mere toolkit or niche expertise. Instead, the focus is on fostering an understanding of BIM as a holistic concept that involves process optimization, and effective information management. Based on the scenarios for BIM's impact, the survey reveals the prevalence of simpler scenarios: (scenario 1) incorporating BIM into education as modeling tools, (scenario 2) the improvement of construction management methods and (scenario 3) to the integration of BIM tools within specific course contexts. Moreover, the respondents have identified the need for overcoming technical barriers, promoting real-time practical experience, improving

collaboration between disciplines, and highlighting the broader importance of BIM principles beyond just software tools, thus highlighting BIM as a tool that breaks down the professional silos not just in construction engineering practice but in education as well.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/WEUVjdS7xHA>

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